

Interfacial bond strength between SiC Monofilaments and spray-deposited titanium

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ABSTRACT

The single fibre pull-out test has been used to characterize the bonding between SiC monofilaments and a spray-deposited titanium matrix. The matrix was deposited by the Vacuum Plasma Deposition process and, as the tests were carried out on specimens in the as-deposited state, little or no interfacial reaction had taken place. Pull-out test data are provided for both the tungsten-cored "Sigma" and the carbon-cored AVCO "SCS-6" monofilaments. In addition, an examination was made of the effect on bond strength of a thin (750 nm) coating of Y/Y_2O_3 sputtered onto the fibre. Considerably greater adhesion was exhibited with the uncoated Sigma fibre with respect to the AVCO fibre. This may be related to the differences in the surface chemistry and microstructure of the two fibres. It was also found that the coated Sigma fibre exhibited similar bond strengths to the uncoated fibre.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Spray Deposition to form composites

Spray deposition to form metal matrix composites is now an established technique [1-4], although there is very little information in the literature about the possibility of forming composites reinforced with discontinuous or continuous fibres by this process. In the current work, the process of Vacuum Plasma Spraying (VPS) is used to deposit a titanium matrix material around arrays of continuous, monofilamentary reinforcement, to form composite laminae. Compared with melt atomization processes, VPS is similar in involving the impingement of a stream of molten metal droplets, but differs in offering much higher droplet velocities, a more controlled chemical environment and a greater versatility in terms of control over the thermal field [5-8]. In spray deposition onto a fibre array, the droplet/fibre thermal excursion is very transient, typical droplet solidification times being in the order of 100 μ s [8] - probably too brief for any progressive reaction in the Ti/SiC system [9] depending on the post spraying thermal history of the deposit. This process, therefore, offers the prospect of producing Ti/SiC composite systems with little or no interfacial reaction product in the as-fabricated condition.

Fibre barrier coatings [10] are attracting increasing interest as a possible solution to the inevitable fibre/matrix reactivity problems [11-13]. In this work, the role of a thin sputter-deposited Y barrier layer is examined in terms of its influence on fibre/matrix bonding. In addition, examination of the failed interface should give a qualitative assessment of the relative fibre/coating and coating/matrix bond strengths.

1.2. The Single Fibre Pull-Out Test

Clearly, the exact nature of the fibre-matrix interface is of great importance in determining composite properties. The strength of the bond affects both stress transfer efficiency and fracture behaviour. While inefficient stress transfer may be of less importance to the axial properties of continuously-reinforced material, weak bonding may lead to poor transverse properties. Bonding may arise from various sources including wetting (Van der Waals forces), mechanical keying, and may be affected by residual stresses (particularly the radial stress and the hydrostatic component of the stress state at the interface). In practice, it is very difficult to characterize the mechanical properties of the interface with any accuracy. With multiple fibres present, it is difficult to relate macroscopic behaviour to interfacial properties. Often, one is reduced to inferences from qualitative observations on fibre fracture, matrix cracking or voiding behaviour in individual localities, which is haphazard at best. As an example, one of the few estimates of the interfacial adhesive shear strength, τ_a , in a Ti/SiC fibrous composite [14] was made by observing the length to which fibres tended to break up under applied stress and assuming that this represented a fraction of the critical aspect ratio. This yielded a value of 200 MPa, but the technique is clearly prone to serious error.

The single fibre pull-out test, although often difficult to carry out, can give much more specific information. A schematic diagram showing the pull-out test geometry and the distribution of axial stress in the fibre, is given in fig. 1. The technique has the advantage of providing an unambiguous method of determining the interfacial shear strength, τ_a . It also gives information about radial stress and frictional characteristics. Careful design of the test geometry is necessary, however, to avoid problems of misalignment, and to avoid damaging the exposed monofilament.

Fig. 1 Schematic Diagram of the Single Fibre Pull-Out Test.

Fig. 2. Schematic Representation of an Idealized Pull-Out Curve.

A schematic diagram of an idealized pull-out curve (stress against displacement) is shown in fig. 2. In principle, several interfacial properties can be deduced: τ_a (from the debonding stress), the interfacial radial stress σ_r , and the coefficient of friction μ (from frictional pull-out). However, interpretation requires care. In the analysis of this system, it is common to use a version of the shear lag analysis, broadly following a number of previous treatments [15-23]:

$$\frac{d\sigma_f}{dx} = \frac{-E_m(U_R - U_r)}{(1+\nu_m)r^2 \ln\{R/r\}} \quad (1)$$

where σ_f is the fibre stress, x is the distance into the matrix, E_m is the modulus of the matrix, U_r & U_R are matrix displacements at the interface and far-field respectively and ν_m is the Poisson's ratio of the matrix.

Assumptions are made of perfect interfacial bonding (up to the point of debonding) and that the remote matrix is unstrained. (It is worth noting that this latter point may depend on gripping conditions.) Differentiating equation (1) and solving with the boundary conditions; $\sigma_f = \sigma_{f0}$ at $x = 0$, and $\sigma_f = 0$ at $x = L$, gives the following stress distribution:

$$\sigma_f = \sigma_{f0} \left\{ \frac{\sinh(n(L-x)/r)}{\sinh(nL/r)} \right\} \quad (2)$$

in which n is a dimensionless constant:

$$n^2 = \frac{E_m}{E_f(1+\nu_m) \ln(R/r)} \quad (3)$$

A diagrammatic representation of this distribution is shown in figure 1. Debonding therefore takes place at the point where the maximum shear stress operates, i.e. at $x = 0$, since:

$$\tau_{imax} = -\frac{r}{2} \left\{ \frac{d\sigma_f}{dx} \right\}_{x=0} = \frac{n \sigma_{f0}}{2} \coth \left\{ \frac{nL}{r} \right\} \quad (4)$$

In principle therefore, a value for τ_{imax} ($= \tau_a$) may be obtained from a single test, using the debonding stress, σ_{f0d} , in this expression. (It is, however, preferable to obtain σ_{f0d} values for a range of L values.)

After debonding, frictional pull-out will occur due to the contact pressure on the fibre. It can be shown that:

$$\sigma_{f0} = \frac{-\sigma_r E_f}{\nu_f E_m} \{1 - \exp(-BL)\} \quad (5)$$

where σ_r is assumed to be negative (compressive) and B is given by

$$B = \frac{2 \mu \nu_f E_m}{E_f r} \quad (6)$$

in which μ is the (dynamic) coefficient of friction.

Equation (5) defines the shape of the frictional part of the pull-out curve and in principle, both σ_r and μ can be found from the values of σ_{f0} for two selected instantaneous embedded depths. In order to have any confidence in this procedure, it would be necessary to ensure that the shape of the experimental curve conformed well with the predicted one.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. The Pull-Out Test Geometry

The design of the pull-out specimen is shown in figure 3. This design fulfils the requirements of fabrication by the VPS process and also attempts to address the problems of fibre alignment and fibre gripping. In the VPS process, the gas temperature in the vicinity of the substrate is very high (possibly ~3000 K), but the relatively large thermal mass of the substrate, in conjunction with a good thermal conduction path, means that this assembly often remains relatively cool (~500 K).

Figure 3. The Single Fibre Pull-Out Specimen.

The use of a thin CP-Ti backing foil provides rigidity, while keeping the assembly weight low. The problem of fibre misalignment is addressed by gripping the matrix via two circular holes in the CP-Ti backing foil. The fibre should be coaxial with the line joining the centre of the two holes. The deposition geometry is very similar to that during normal composite fabrication. A titanium backing foil was used to avoid differential thermal contraction stresses between substrate and deposit.

To effect fibre pull-out, the foil must be split along a line normal to the fibre axis and passing through the centre of the large central hole, thus allowing the two halves to be pulled apart. Only one end of the fibre will pull-out, the other end being simply held in its surrounding matrix. As the initial pull-out response is elastic, any deformation of the fibre end remaining embedded should not affect the pull-out curve, but will simply act as a machine compliance. (The chances of both fibres pulling out simultaneously is very small). A further feature of the test is that the observed bond strengths are lower bounds from, effectively, twice the number of tests actually carried out.

To keep the overall substrate temperature low, the assembly in figure 3 was clamped to a large copper block (using copper strips), which also acted to shield the relevant areas of the specimen. About 500 µm of commercially-pure titanium was deposited onto the assembly. The temperature of the copper block increased gradually during deposition up to a maximum of about 250°C. As the titanium foil was in close contact with this block, it is assumed that the maximum specimen temperature was not very much higher than this. In the work briefly reported here, several pull-out specimens were produced, containing lengths of AVCO SCS-6 SiC monofilament, tungsten-cored "Sigma" SiC monofilament and Sigma monofilament coated with approximately 750 nm of yttrium.

2.3. Single Fibre Pull-Out Testing

In the as-sprayed state, the assembly is prone to mechanical damage, and division of the backing foil was only attempted when the assembly was in place in the mechanical testing machine. The method used was to join the assembly with epoxy adhesive prior to spraying and then to dissolve this (with a solution of a commercial paint stripper ("Nitromors") and water), while on the testing machine.

Pull-out testing was performed using a screw-driven mechanical testing machine, fitted with a 50 N load cell. Displacement of the assembly was measured by a linear voltage displacement transducer mounted on the crossheads.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Microstructural Observations

Fig. 4 is an optical micrograph of a Sigma fibre sprayed with titanium. This illustrates the low porosity levels obtainable with the VPS technique. It should be noted, however, that interfacial porosity levels may be considerably higher than this. Fig. 5 shows a backscattered SEM micrograph of the pulled-out section of coated fibre. The (atomic number) contrast clearly illustrates that the coating has remained essentially intact and in good contact with the filament. The presence of the coating on the fibre implies that the fibre/coating bonding may be somewhat greater than that of the coating/matrix interface.

Fig. 4. Optical Micrograph of a Sigma Fibre Sprayed with Ti

Fig. 5. Backscattered SEM micrograph of the pulled-out coated fibre.

3.2. The Pull-Out Curves

The pull-out curve (load vs. displacement) for the Sigma monofilament is shown in fig. 6. A similar curve for the AVCO fibre is shown in fig. 7. A notable feature of these curves is that the Sigma fibre has a much more classical debonding response than the AVCO fibre. Also note the gradually rising background load, which is particularly clear in fig. 7. This is due to a progressive decrease in the extent to which the compression of the LVDT spring is offsetting the tensile load. This is actually present in both tests, but in the case of the AVCO curve the linearity of this effect was slightly masked by a small amount of frictional drag offered by the (partially) dissolved epoxy. The lack of linearity of the initial elastic response in the Sigma plot is due to lateral movement of the gripping assembly as it is initially loaded. This caused a lateral transducer plunger movement, and hence seems to give a smaller displacement than is the case. Both of these sources of experimental error are currently being eliminated by minor improvements to the testing procedure.

Fig. 6. The Pull-Out Curve Obtained from the Sigma Monofilament.

Fig. 7. The Pull-Out Curve Obtained from the AVCO Monofilament.

Ideally, it should be possible to obtain estimates for τ_a , μ & σ_R from a pull-out curve. Using the pull-out curves in figs 6 & 7, values of the debonding load of 3.1 N and 0.35 N for the Sigma and AVCO fibres respectively, are obtained after allowance for the transducer spring response. Using these loads, values for τ_a can be calculated using equation (4); these values are displayed in Table I.

Fibre	L (mm)	r (μm)	n	σ_{fod} (MPa)	τ_a (MPa)
Sigma	0.4	50	0.268	395	61
AVCO	1.0	70	0.284	23	4
Sigma+Y	1.5	50	0.268	445	68

Table I. Estimates of τ_a From the Pull-Out Tests.

Values for L were deduced from SEM examination of the pulled-out fibre lengths. Although the measured peak loads cannot be regarded as very accurate (particularly for the AVCO) it does seem clear that the adhesive shear strength is much higher for the Sigma fibre. With regard to deductions about the radial stress and sliding frictional characteristics, the shape of the curves do not conform to the idealized shape in a way that encourages detailed analysis. It is possible that the apparently low loads (in both cases) during the frictional pull-out period is a reflection of very low (compressive) residual stresses. This may be partially due the effects of slight porosity, or the absence of a massive surrounding matrix, particularly on the underside of the fibres. In addition, the relatively small difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion for this system, coupled with the fact that much of the matrix cooling occurred before the fibre was completely surrounded, means that the compressive radial stress expected from differential thermal contraction might indeed be relatively small.

3.3. Discussion of Results

The calculated values for τ_a in section 3.2. are based on the assumption of uniform interfacial bonding over the fibre circumference. However, the spray deposition process does give the problem of a varying droplet contact pressure over the fibre surface. For example, the droplet contact pressure on the the top surface will be large, while the sides and under surfaces of the fibre will become enveloped by lateral liquid motion, probably with reduced impact velocity. Hence, with this deposition process one is faced with the possibility of a variation of bonding mechanism around the fibre circumference. The bonding mechanisms outlined in section 1.2. may be sensitive to the liquid contact conditions, variations in any interfacial porosity and in matrix mass distribution, and the thermal history around the fibre. The values of τ_a therefore represent average values over the fibre circumference for this particular experimental arrangement.

This technique does, however, provide the possibility for measuring average τ_a values for "clean" (i.e. unreacted) Ti/SiC interfaces, and in this case has revealed a large difference between the bonding of the Sigma fibre with the titanium matrix, and the AVCO fibre with the same matrix. Examination of the two pull-out curves, given in figs 6 & 7, reveals that the AVCO fibre has very little inherent adhesion. The Sigma fibre on the other hand, shows a clear debonding peak, and a larger frictional pull-out stress. As the two specimens were sprayed and tested under exactly similar conditions, it seems reasonable to assume that these radical differences in bonding are due to the differences in surface chemistry of the fibres.

The Sigma fibre is composed of uniformly stoichiometric β -SiC, although at the surface a very thin SiO₂ layer may be present. The AVCO fibre, on the other hand, has a varying SiC stoichiometry. The periphery of this fibre is deliberately made C-rich, to form an amorphous C layer about 2-3 μm thick [24,25]. The outer surface deviates back towards SiC stoichiometry and forms a layer about 100 nm thick of α and β -SiC and amorphous C. It therefore seems reasonable to assume that the lack of bonding and the rather low coefficient of friction of the AVCO fibre is due to this C-rich surface chemistry. Presumably, the surface layers offer little resistance to shear.

In contrast to this, work by Vassel et al. [14] on the measurement of interfacial bonding between an AVCO fibre and a Ti-6Al-4V matrix in the as-fabricated condition (diffusion-bonded), has suggested interfacial shear strengths in the order of 200 MPa. The experimental method, however, relies on internal fragmentation of the fibre after straining the composite. This is assumed to generate a distribution of fibre lengths between L_c and $L_c/2$ (where L_c is the critical fibre aspect ratio) and the average length is taken as $3L_c/4$. From this value τ_a can be found. It should be noted however, that this technique requires an accurate knowledge of the fibre fracture stress *in the composite*. This fracture stress will probably be influenced by the compressive axial differential thermal contraction stresses after fabrication. More importantly, as the typical fabrication thermal history generates 1-2 μm of interfacial reaction product [12], the results of the current work seem to suggest that the bonding of the AVCO fibre to the titanium matrix is dominated by interfacial reaction product formation. Other comparative work using the same technique [26] has found that, in the diffusion-bonded condition, Sigma fibres generate a bond strength of about 350 MPa, compared to 200 MPa for the AVCO fibres.

The results for the coated fibre suggest that the coating has not given rise to impaired bond strength. The zone of failure is clearly limited to the coating/matrix interface rather than the coating/fibre interface.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A variant of the single fibre pull-out test has been developed for metal matrix composites produced by spray deposition. The main problems in applying the conventional test to MMCs arise from the brittleness of the large diameter monofilaments employed, and the stiffness and strength of the matrix. As a result of these factors, handling and gripping of the fibre are fraught with danger of premature fibre fracture, often at the point where it emerges from the matrix. In the version described, the test is carried out by spraying both ends of the fibre and supporting the assembly on a thin backplate while handling and locating in the testing machine. The backplate is in two halves, held together either by glue or by the frictional forces from two pairs of magnets. In the former case, the glue is dissolved prior to testing, and in the latter the contribution to the load from the frictional motion of the magnets is subtracted after running a test in the absence of the fibre. As an example of the use of this test, data are presented from two specimens of "Sigma" and "AVCO" SiC monofilaments, in the as-sprayed condition after deposition of (CP) titanium using Vacuum Plasma Spray equipment. In this condition, there is a negligible degree of interfacial chemical reaction in both cases, in contrast to available SiC/Ti composites produced by diffusion bonding. It was found that the interfacial adhesive shear strength was about 50 MPa for the Sigma fibre, but was less than 5 MPa for the AVCO fibre. These data have been briefly considered in the light of known information about the surface chemistry and structure of the two fibres. In addition a single fibre pull-out test was performed with a fibre coated with 750 nm of Y/Y₂O₃. It has been shown that the interfacial bond strength is unaffected by the presence of this coating and that failure is predominantly on the coating/matrix interface.

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3. Thermal Effect and Hygrothermal Effect

THEORY OF THE
ELECTRIC